

The Interplay between India and Afghanistan: Role of Non-State Actors in fostering separatist tendencies in the restive Province of Baluchistan

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Abstract: *As a part of broader geopolitical competition, India and Afghanistan are destabilizing Pakistan through their active involvement in Pakistan's restive province: Baluchistan. India and Afghanistan's interference aim at derailing China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC)- a flagship project of China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). Baluchistan has an important geostrategic location not only in the context of these projects but also as a resource rich province of Pakistan. It is therefore imperative to counter these proxies with an iron -hand. This research work critically examines the multifaceted dynamics of Baluchistan's internal security environment through the lens of external influences, focusing on Afghanistan and India as key actors involved in Baluchistan. The study concludes that Pakistan's state response, though resilient, remains largely reactive and securitized, constrained by institutional fragmentation and inadequate narrative management. To achieve sustainable stability, the research proposes an integrated framework emphasizing diplomatic engagement, intelligence coordination, and socio-economic development.*

Keywords: *Proxy war, Separatism, CPEC, Baluchistan*

Introduction

Pakistan occupies a uniquely strategic position at the intersection of South Asia, Central Asia, and the Middle East. Since 1947, Pakistan's security environment has been shaped not only by its domestic dynamics but also by the competing strategic interests of neighbouring states and global powers. Historical legacies, such as partition, territorial disputes, ideological polarization, and the enduring rivalry with India, have continuously influenced the country's internal stability and external relationships. For decades, Pakistan has been confronted by internal strife and violence leading to political and economic stability. India and Afghanistan are major actors in fomenting instability in Pakistan. A plethora of study reflects that both countries are actively involved in destabilization of Baluchistan. Both India

and Afghanistan share geographical, cultural and historical ties. Under the pretext of these ties, both countries intervene inside Pakistan. Afghanistan's long-running instability has often spilled across the border into Pakistan through militant sanctuaries, refugee flows, and ideological spill-over (Choudhary, Hanif, & Awan, 2022). Meanwhile, India's strategic posture towards Pakistan has expanded beyond conventional rivalry into hybrid and proxy warfare, leveraging non-state actors, information operations, and regional networks (Matloob, Matloob, & Ishaq, 2023; Askari & Niazi, 2022).

The transformation of warfare in the 21st century, from conventional state conflict to a blend of cyber operations, economic coercion, information campaigns, and insurgency tactics, has altered the nature of security threats facing Pakistan. Analysts argue that Pakistan is exposed to "hybrid warfare" directed at its vulnerabilities rather than simply its conventional defence (Qureshi & Khalid, 2024). In this context, Pakistan's internal security cannot be disentangled from the foreign policy and strategic designs of its neighbors.

Since 2010, Afghanistan and India have emerged as active players influencing Pakistan's domestic stability. The Taliban resurgence in Afghanistan and the reopening of India's diplomatic and economic engagement in Afghanistan have amplified Pakistan's concern over trans-border militancy and strategic encirclement (Choudhary et al., 2022; Noor ul Islam, Jafar & Yasmine, 2023). Concurrently, Indian-initiated information campaigns and covert support for indigenous insurgent movements have been identified as factors undermining Pakistan's internal cohesion (Akhtar, Jan & Akram, 2021).

The main issue this research study is going to solve is the dual vulnerability of Pakistan, the weaknesses within the system of governance and development of Baluchistan and the external situation of exploiting these weaknesses by Afghanistan and India through hybrid and proxy action. This inter-linked dynamic, where foreign influence exploits internal fault-lines and internal vulnerabilities enable foreign interference, illustrates that Pakistan's

internal conflicts cannot be understood in isolation. They must be analyzed through the lens of regional power politics, hybrid threat frameworks, and state resilience. This study posits that the intersection of external influence and domestic fragility constitutes a fundamental challenge to Pakistan's security and governance.

Geostrategic Significance of Pakistan and Great Power Rivalries

Pakistan holds significant geopolitical importance due to its strategic location, nuclear status, role in major infrastructure projects, and position amid great-power rivalries. Pakistan's location makes it a natural bridge in connectivity between Asia's sub-regions, influencing trade, energy corridors, and military logistics. Pakistan sits at the crossroads of South Asia and Central Asia. Pakistan has an access to Arabian Sea and proximity to Strait of Hormuz- vital for global oil transit. For China, CPEC- a corridor that connects Gwadar in Pakistan with China's Xinjiang province- provides strategic access to the Indian Ocean, secures energy routes, and counters encirclement concerns.

It forms a center of international rivalry. The United States, China, and Russia are all foreign actors who have traditionally utilized the territory of Pakistan and alliances as a tool to pursue their geopolitical interests (Wolf, 2020). The alliances and associations of SEATO and CENTO during the Cold War made Pakistan orient towards the United States in this bid to offset the Soviet-backed rise of India. These alignments, however, also put Pakistan in the path of proxy warfare, especially in Afghanistan, where it became the frontline state in the fight against the Soviet Union (Abbas, 2019). Militarization of society, influx of the refugees, and the rise of the extremist ideologies of that time created a lasting tendency of internal weakness in connection with the external associations.

Following 9/11, Pakistan once more became a primary ally in the War on Terror, being led by the U.S. Although this collaboration resulted in financial aid and international validation, it also resulted in some drastic domestic outcomes: insurgencies, polarization of the political

situation, and vengeful violence of armed forces (Yousaf, 2020). According to the scholars, the U.S. policies, drone strikes, and pressure to act against local militants worsened the domestic divides and undermined the state authority in the tribal regions (Haider, 2020).

At the same time, the United States' strategic alliance with India, which was manifested in the Civil Nuclear Agreement of 2008 and increasing defense collaboration, changed the balance of power in the region. Pakistan felt this change as a threat to its deterrence stability and was further pushed to China in strategic balancing (Mahmood & Bashir, 2021). The Chinese investments in Pakistan that have been reinforced by the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) have solidified the economic and infrastructure foundation of this country, yet it has also turned into a point of contention between different world powers (Wolf, 2020). The US withdrawal from Afghanistan once again left a vacuum which was filled by non-state actors and undemocratic forces further exacerbating security situation in Pakistan. Weak and unstable Afghanistan poses a significant challenge because Afghan soil is being used against Pakistan. Pakistan has time again warned Afghanistan that its land should not be used against Pakistan but to no avail.

In addition, Iran and the Gulf states have a subtle but major role to play in the internal conflicts in Pakistan. The polarization along sectarian lines in Pakistan has at times reflected regional tensions between Saudi Arabia and Iran, especially the fundraising network and ideological outreach (Youseaf, 2020). These transnational forces depict the way international and regional rivalries have infiltrated the national and regional borders of Pakistan to play out in the internal politics of identity, religious belonging, and localized sources of authority.

India's Involvement in Fomenting Separatism in Baluchistan

India's proxy war and financial assistance to the separatist groups in Pakistan is secret to none. The intelligence reports and international testifiers, including the ones submitted to the

United Nations, have indicated that the Baloch militants have been funded by the Indians and trained via networks that exist within Afghanistan (Raza & Mustafa, 2023). Though India refutes these accusations, the continued existence of the separatist propaganda in the form of cross-border media and diaspora organizations indicates India's involvement in unrest in Baluchistan. A dossier submitted to the UN indicates that India is playing a significant role in fomenting separatism in Baluchistan, Pakistan's largest province, which has faced intermittent insurgencies since 1947. India's intelligence agency, the Research and Analysis Wing (RAW), provides financial, logistical, and military support to Baloch separatist groups such as the Baluchistan Liberation Army (BLA) and Baloch Liberation Front (BLF).

Some of the recent cases justifying Pakistan's stance are described below.

i. Kulbhushan Jadhav Arrest (2016)

Kulbhushan Jadhav- an Indian national and a retired Indian Navy commander- was arrested by Pakistani authorities in Baluchistan in 2016. After investigation, he was confirmed as a serving officer attached to India's external intelligence agency, Research and Analysis Wing (RAW), operating under the alias "Hussein Mubarak Patel" with a fake passport. Further interrogation of revealed that he had been imparting Naval fighting training to Baloch separatists. These separatists were trained with an objective to target Pakistani ports. The military termed his capture the "proof of Indian interference and state-sponsored terrorism". He was tried in a Field General Court Martial with charges of espionage, sabotage and terrorism charges. He Court Martial sentence him to death as Jadhav could not defend himself against the charges. According to an influential Indian journal, FRONTLINE, "Jadhav may be a serving Indian Navy officer and that India is waging a covert war against Pakistan". It shows that there is no denying the fact that india is using its resources to promote instability in Pakistan. In a press release, Ministry of Foreign Affairs noted "the arrest of Indian RAW agent Kulbhushan Jadhav

from Baluchistan and his confessional statement admitting involvement in activities aimed at destabilizing Pakistan, and support to terrorist elements vindicated Pakistan's longstanding position about India's involvement in such activities.

ii. Dossier on Indian Interference and Terrorism

Time and again, Pakistan raises serious concerns about India's involvement in Baluchistan at the United Nation organization. Pakistan has also presented evidence to the United Nations that India has been actively involved in Pakistan but to no avail. In 2016 and 2017, Pakistan presented a dossier to the UN proving its stance that India is involved in destabilization of Baluchistan. The dossier provided empirical evidence that India provides \$22 million to Baloch Liberation Army and Tehrik e Taliban Pakistan. The dossier also indicated that such an amount is being used in carrying out attacks on Pakistani nationals as well as Chinese workers who are Associated with CPEC projects. The PLA and TTP. Um, use tactics such as bombing and associated assassinations to destabilize Baluchistan. The dossier reflects that India is leaving no stone unturned in creating unrest in Baluchistan.

iii. Khuzdar School Bus Attack, 2025

In 2025, A school bus was attacked in Khuzdar, Baluchistan. It was a suicide attack, claimed by Baluch Liberation Army. After initial investigation, Pakistan Reached a conclusion that the attack was orchestrated by Indian backed Baloch Liberation Army. Pakistan's Defense Minister Waja Asif said that Indian proxy is actively engaged in Afghanistan and their sole aim is to destabilize Baluchistan. He further added that the link between Baloch Liberation Army and Indian intelligence agency RAW is now a well-known fact. He also added that Baloch Liberation Army works as an Indian proxy in Pakistan. The link between RAW and Baluch Liberation Army is that RAW gives money while BLA unleash atrocities. The PM office declared the attack as coward act. The office also added that the attack reflects India's uneasiness with Baluchistan success in the context of game changer project- CPEC. Pakistan

categorically mentioned India that that the attack was carried out by state sponsored proxies (Fitna Al Hindustan) of India which the world has largely come to know as epicenter of instability in the region.

iv. Train Hijacking by BLA (2025)

On March 11, Baloch separatists hijacked a passenger train carrying more than 400 passengers from Quetta to Peshawar. The incident shocked Pakistan and was strongly condemned by the United Nations as a "heinous act of terrorism." The Baloch Liberation Army (BLA) claimed responsibility for the attack. Pakistani military spokesperson says that at least 31 people, including civilians and security personnel, as well as 33 militants, were killed in the action. The attack once highlighted a broader network between India, Afghanistan and BLA. India provided financial and logistical support while Afghanistan provided advanced weapons which were left behind by the United States after its withdrawal. The hijacking of passenger trains in Pakistan is entirely unprecedented. Attacks by Baloch militants (including the Baloch Liberation Army) have mostly targeted buses and other road transport in the region. Such attacks are not possible without full-fledged support from India and Afghanistan. India's growing concerns are testament to the fact that its proxies are now not allowing innocent civilians to travel to and from Baluchistan.

Afghanistan's involvement in and use of its soil against Pakistan

Pakistan and Afghanistan did not enjoy cordially relations for over seven decades. However, the relationship reached to all time after US invasion of Afghanistan in 2001. The post-2001 events caused a crisis in internal security like never before. A porous border has been used by militant groups like Al-Qaeda, the Haqqani Network, and Tehreek-e-Taliban Pakistan (TTP) to turn the tribal belt of Pakistan into an insurgency theatre (Youseaf, 2020). U.S. drone attacks also contributed to distrust among the local people, adding to anti-state feelings. Therefore, the internal wars in Afghanistan always echoed through the Durand Line, strengthening the image

of Pakistan as a haven and victim of transnational militancy. The U.S. troop withdrawal in 2021 had already taken root in the political and social life of Pakistan because the instability had become embedded in Afghanistan. The Taliban succession that followed changed the balance of power in the region again. Although Islamabad initially received the regime well, the resurgence of the TTP militants on Afghan territory quickly revived the security issue (Choudhary et al., 2022).

The following major threats are emanating from Afghanistan which cause unrest in Pakistan specifically in Baluchistan.

i. Cross-Border Safe Havens

Afghan territory became a haven for militants to escape Pakistani military operations like Rah-e-Nijat and Zarb-e-Azb. This mountainous geography and the poor structure of the Afghan governance enabled TTP to re-form and re-initiate attacks across the border (Haider, 2020). These groups are involved in terrorist activities in Pakistan in general and Baluchistan in Particular.

ii. Ideological Convergence

Afghan and Pakistani Taliban are both inspired by Deobandi interpretations of the Muslim faith, which enables the cross-border recruiting and collaboration of the groups. Pakistan's Radical madrassas of the frontiers of Pakistan are considered the ideological bridge between the two movements (Rashid, 2021). Therefore, it is easier for terrorist groups to create a terrorist network across the Durand Line.

iii. Economic Interdependence

Smuggling of fuel, narcotics, and weapons and the informal border economy give militant groups financial support. Such a parallel economy weakens the fiscal control of Pakistan and continues

to promote corruption in the border-enforcing structures (Abbas, 2019). The war economy is being used in orchestrating terrorist attacks in Baluchistan. Pakistan has warned Afghan authorities to deal these groups with iron hand. Pakistan also demands that Afghan soil should not be used against Pakistan. But Afghan authorities failed to address these reservations. Afghan authorities' failure to act against terrorist groups reflect that Afghanistan is itself part of the game to destabilize Pakistan.

iv. Tribal and Ethnic Networks

The tribal loyalties, like the Pashtun belt, disregard the state border. Militant accounts do play on these ethnic solidarities, but position conflict as a defense of Pashtun honor instead of terrorism (Yousaf, 2020). Such a network makes it difficult for Pakistan's security forces to differentiate between local people and terrorists. Making advantage of same identity, terrorists attack local people and security forces using Afghan territory. These linkages increased when the Taliban took over in 2021. Despite the leaders of the Afghan Taliban issuing threats not to intervene in the internal affairs of Pakistan, the TTP once again initiated an insurgency campaign after being inspired by the Taliban victory on the Afghan soil (Choudhary et al., 2022).

Terrorist Attacks in Baluchistan since Taliban Takeover

Afghanistan has become a haven from terrorist attacks in Baluchistan. Pakistan has warned the new Taliban government again to take punitive measures against such havens, but so far Afghan government has not paid any heed to Pakistan's requests. Prior to the current Afghan government, terrorism was at all time low (Global Terrorism Index). But afterwards, terrorism has become an existential threat for Pakistan. Below is year wise list of terrorist attacks in Baluchistan specifically by Tehrik e Taliban Pakistan.

i. Terrorist Incidents in 2021

Pakistan experienced numerous terrorist attacks in 2021. Members of religious minorities faced significant threats from terrorist groups. The following examples are some of the more-destructive and higher-profile attacks and demonstrate a variety of methods, targets, and perpetrators:

- In January, 11 Shias were killed in Kachi district. It was claimed by ISIS-K.
- In another terrorist incident five persons were killed in a suicide attack in the parking lot of the Serena hotel in Quetta, Baluchistan. It was claimed by TTP.
- a well-known journalist was killed in an explosion in Hub, Baluchistan. The BLA claimed responsibility.

ii. Terrorist Incidents in 2022

Pakistan experienced increased terrorist attacks in 2022.

- In February, militants attacked two Pakistani paramilitary bases in Baluchistan. The BLA claimed responsibility for the coordinated attacks. At least 4 soldiers lost their lives.
- In another incident in April, a woman exploded herself outside the Confucius Institute in Karachi, killing five employees.

iii. Terrorist Incidents in 2023

Pakistan faced a significant increase in the number of terrorist attacks in 2023, compared with 2022. The following examples are among the more destructive and higher-profile incidents and show a variety of methods, targets, and perpetrators:

- In September, 60 people lost their lives when a suicide bomber exploded himself during a religious procession in Mastung, Baluchistan.
- In March, A suicide bomber rammed a motorcycle into a police truck, killing nine policemen in Sibbi.

- In April Four people were killed in a bombing targeting a police vehicle in a marketplace in Quetta on April 10. In a successive attack, a station house officer was targeted in a roadside blast in Quetta. (Aljazeera.com)

iv. Terrorist Incidents in 2024

- Right before the general elections, two twin blasts jolted Baluchistan, killing at least 27 innocent people while more than 20 people got injured. The attacks targeted political parties which were preparing for the general elections. The ISIL group claimed responsibility for the blasts. The proscribed group is active in Afghanistan.
- In August 2024, the Baluchistan Liberation Army (BLA) launched a series of attacks in Baluchistan. The attacks were carried out against civilian lorry drivers as well as military installations and police officers, killing at least 74 people, mostly unarmed civilians, and wounding many more.
- In November, BLA once again attacked innocent people at Quetta Railway Station. The attack killed at least 32 people while dozens more injured.

v. Terrorist Incidents in 2025

- In January two soldiers and five militants were killed in an attack on a security outpost in Killa Abdullah District.
- Eighteen members of the Frontier Corps were killed in an attack by the Baluchistan on their vehicle near Mangochar, Kalat District, Baluchistan.
- On February 9, Seven people were killed in an attack by gunmen on a bus in Barkhan District, Baluchistan. The Baluchistan Liberation Army subsequently claimed responsibility
- In another well organized and planned attack Jaffer express was hijacked where more than 400 passengers were held hostages.

- Likewise, seven soldiers were killed in a bomb attack on a military vehicle in Machh, Kachhi District, Baluchistan. The BLA claimed responsibility.
- A suicide bomber drove an explosive-laden vehicle into a school bus transporting students of the Army Public School, Khuzdar, killing eight people, including 4 children.

Way Forward: How to counter two-front threats?

In the year 2024 and 2025, terrorist incidents in Baluchistan increased sharply. There is significant changes in tactics being used by the insurgent groups. For example, these group recruit female as suicide bombers. In a culturally rigid society, it is very difficult to differentiate between local women and a terrorist. There is a chance that insurgent groups will continue attacking security forces and innocent people in Baluchistan in 2026 as well. However, if the following measures are taken, there is a possibility that terrorist threats emanating from India and Afghanistan countered.

i. Institutional Integration

Hybrid threats are complex and require whole-of-government coordination. Pakistan needs to form a permanent civilian and military representation of the National Security Council

Secretariat with connections between the ministries of foreign, defence, interior, and finance, under a singular strategy (Mahmood & Bashir, 2021). This organization would not act as a consultation center but as a functional center of intelligence compilation, strategic projections, and policy implementations.

ii.Enhancing Inter-Agency Intelligence Co-operation

The phenomenon of hybrid war removes the line between domestic and external threats. To mitigate this, intelligence agencies, including ISI, IB, FIA, and NACTA, are to come up with analytical units on cyber, financial, and informational threats in collaboration (Matloob et al., 2023). Lack of a central database prevents interagency correlation of threats. This can be sealed through the use of an integrated intelligence grid that has common access protocols.

iii.The Foreign Office should be revitalized

The Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MoFA) in Pakistan needs to be transformed into both a think-and-do tank instead of a diplomatic bureaucracy. Prompt narrative management would be possible through the establishment of special Desks of Hybrid Diplomacy, Public Diplomacy, and Strategic Foresight. The diplomatic training should cover the modules of media strategy, data analytics, and international lawfare (Haider, 2020).

iv.Civil-Military Synergy towards Foreign Policy

Civil-military divergence is an issue that continues to emerge across the strategic behavior of Pakistan. The balance can be established through institutionalizing civilian control, but with military consultation, not without it. The National Security Policy (2022) was a measure in this direction, but its implementation needs to be operational commitment between ministries (Youseaf, 2020). This kind of coordination is critical to stop the reversal of policies, and also the diplomatic signaling should be in line with the security objectives

v.Regional Confidence-Building Measures

The isolation and constant rivalry cannot give birth to sustainable security in Pakistan. The local setting- characterized by the opposing alignments, boundaries, and polarization of ideologies requires confidence-building measures (CBMs) that reduce mistrust and enable effective collaboration.

vi.Cybersecurity Architecture

There should be a National Cyber Command Authority in Pakistan, which should consist of the integration of the defence, intelligence, and civilian IT sectors. This body will be involved in the coordination of cyber threat identification, digital forensics, and information protection (Matloob et al., 2023). The current cyber laws should be brought up to date and criminalize cross-border data manipulation and put in place jurisdictional cooperation with social media sites.

vii.Strategic Digital Diplomacy and Communication

The contemporary conflict is based on proactive narrative management. Pakistan should establish a Strategic Communication Directorate whose primary duty is the creation and spreading of information about national success, peace campaigns, and anti- extremism. The cooperation of ISPR with MoFA and the academic think tanks can help to increase the coherence of messages (Askari and Niazi, 2022).

viii.Domestic Industrialization and CPEC 2.0

This transition of the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) into the CPEC 2.0 model focuses on the transfer of technology and development of industrial and human development. It is imperative that fruits of second phase of CPEC must reach the poor people of Baluchistan. If resources are equally distributed, there is a possibility that foreign agendas driven against Pakistan can be countered.

Conclusion

Pakistan stands at a decisive crossroads. The coming decade will determine whether it remains ensnared in the cycles of insecurity and reaction or rises as a resilient, forward-looking nation anchored in justice and moderation. The lessons of history are clear: no state can achieve external peace without internal harmony, and no society can ensure stability without equity. The real strength of Pakistan lies not in its weapons or alliances but in its people, their faith, creativity, and will endure. As declared by the Commander of Defense Forces, Field Marshal Gen Asim Munir: “Baluchistan is the destiny of Pakistan”. Pakistan must utilize all its resources to counter internal and external threats which are emanating from India and Afghanistan. It is possible through effective strategy, synergy between civil and military leaderships and empowering people of Baluchistan.

References

- Abbas, H. (2019). *Pakistan's Internal Security Challenges: From Turmoil to Transformation: Routledge*
- Ahmed, Z. (2020). *Baluchistan and the politics of insurgency*. Oxford University Press
- Akhtar, N., Jan, I., & Akram, S. (2021). *Hybrid warfare strategy of India: Impacts on Pakistan*. *Global Regional Review*, 6(2), 45-60.
- Al Jazeera. (2025). *Pakistan–Afghanistan clashes and militant resurgence*. *Al Jazeera News Report*
- Askari, M. U., & Niazi, L. K. (2022). *Indian hybrid war against Pakistan: A strategic theory perspective*. *Journal of Indian Studies*, 8(1), Article 1053.
- Baloch, M. (2018). *History and politics of Baloch nationalism*. Royal Books
- CPEC Secretariat. (2022). *CPEC project updates and security brief*. Government of Pakistan
- Mahmood, A., & Bashir, S. (2021). *Revisiting Realism in South Asia: The persistence of conflict between India and Pakistan*. *Pakistan Journal of International Affairs*, 4(2), 15–33.

Rafiq, A. (2021). Countering extremism through Islamic discourse: Lessons from Pakistan.

Journal of Peace and Religion, 9(2), 43–59

Siddiqi, F. (2020). *The politics of identity and conflict in Balochistan*. Routledge.